

CHARACTERISTICS OF ORGANIZING PUBLIC ARTISTIC SPORTS EVENTS

Nasirdinov Murot Toyshiboevich

Teacher of Namangan state university
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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the reforms in the field of culture, art, music, and sports in our country, organization of mass artistic sports events and their features, components of mass artistic sports events.

Key words: holiday, sport, reform, people, event, youth, public event, spectacle, interest, order.

Аннотация: В статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в сфере культуры, искусства, музыки и спорта в нашей стране, организации массовых художественных спортивных мероприятий и их особенностях, составляющих массовых художественных спортивных мероприятий.

Ключевые слова: праздник, спорт, реформа, народ, событие, молодежь, массовое мероприятие, зрелище, интерес, заказ.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimizda madaniyat, san'at, musiqa, sport sohasidagi islohotlar, ommaviy badiiy sport tadbirlarini tashkil etish va ularning xususiyatlari, ommaviy badiiy sport tadbirlarini komponentlari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: bayram, sport, islohot, xalq, tadbir, yoshlar, ommaviy tadbir, tomoshalar, qiziqish, tartib.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 " On measures for innovative development of the arts ", Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 " On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan", 2019 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1019 of December 19, 2019 "On approval of the Program for improving the activities of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021", November 23, 2019 Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 26, 2019 " On approval of the activities of the Erkin Vakhidov Memorial Museum and the Treasury House Museum" Resolution

of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 630 [1] of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], 2020 “On measures to further enhance the role and influence of the arts in society” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 325 of June 9, 2021 and “Marturs’ Memory” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 357 of February 2, 2022 “On support of the Moat Fund” The normative legal acts adopted, such as Resolution No. PD – 12 of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan [4] are becoming increasingly important.

Holidays of Uzbekistan are becoming real national holidays. Artistic sports holidays are one of these holidays. Nowadays, no matter what kind of public holidays, theatrical mass performances, theatrical concerts, elements of artistic and sports performances are used. Year by year, such holiday performances are becoming more popular and artistically perfected. In particular, the government and the President of our Republic attach great importance to physical education and sports in “raising a perfect person” and “raising a healthy generation”. The organization of sports holidays such as “Hope sprouts”, “Universiade”, which are traditionally held among the youth of our country, is a clear proof of our opinion.

These holidays are not only a sports show or public sports spectacle, but also a form of entertainment and education. In recent years, the dramaturgy of public-sports holidays has developed somewhat, and shows that can give people aesthetic pleasure from the synthesis of art and sports are being created. The value of art and sports shows is determined by their ability to demonstrate past and present events, achievements in science and technology, and human thinking. The main goal of these holidays is to influence people’s minds.

Variety, originality, scalability and other components of the viewership are the main means of achieving the goal. It is difficult to imagine modern public holidays, theatrical shows, and even concerts without elements of public sports shows. Simple, colorful, thematic and emotional effective means of sports have become an irreplaceable style of directors in the process of staging, enriching the shows.

Public sports shows are of great importance in spreading sports and physical education to the general public. Effective tools are constantly evolving.

Light, color, behavior, music are not only complementing the sports action, but also reveal the general idea of the spectacle. The importance of music is increasing more and more[5]. Not only marches and modern pop songs are performed in stadiums, but also classical songs and music.

Mass sports shows include everything characteristic of directing. It is necessary to clarify the ideas, as in the creation of dramatic, opera, ballet and musical performances. However, here the movement is the leader of the management of public sports spectacles, and not only one actor, but a group or a public of many thousands of people participates. Athletes performing public gymnastic performances, background and artistic background groups consisting of several thousand people, and the audience witnessing the events taking place on the field participate in this role.

It is inappropriate to think that the spectacle was created from the independent action of many thousands of different people. Such public celebrations and spectacles are resolved at the level of artistic imagery through the idea of directing. The idea of mass sports spectacle, the imagery of the spectacle is manifested in the ideological connection of episodes and numbers to create a composition. As an example, we can cite the Universiade held in Samarkand in 2004. The main idea of this sports holiday - the role of sports in the struggle for peace, the harmonious development of a person, and a healthy mind in a healthy body - is revealed through the unity of episodes.

Symbols and allegorical images of a whole dramatic direction create the integrity of the composition. The process of searching for and creating new effective tools and compositions for such shows held at the stadium continues. The line-up and re-line-up in the stadium shows have a different meaning than the shows held on the field. Clarity and logic are becoming the most important components in the successful performance of the show, in the symbolic and colorful images, in the transition from image to image, from episode to episode. The different colors of the costumes of the participants, the various objects used in the exercises create a unique image on the field.[6]

Synchronized movements of the participants on the field, public mise-en-scenes increase the level of the spectacle. The seating of the audience in a circle in the stadium presents a difficult task for the director. This arrangement of the audience requires the director to create a suitable composition. To solve this problem, artistic background participants will be placed on opposite stands and the sidewalk will be closed with flag bearers.

Tempo-rhythm image construction is one of the main components of public sports viewing. Its main characteristics are as follows:

- number and duration of episodes to the total audience;
- the rhythmic arrival of consecutive numbers and episodes in time intervals;
- temp - the number of actions in a movement unit;
- a directorial solution in creating a contrast between numbers and episodes, choosing effective means;
- mobility of individual numbers and episodes and their placement in the composition;
- montage - logical combination of episodes, revealing the story of the theme (logical montage), qualitative transition from number to number, from episode to episode (technical montage). The mobility of the tempo depends on how long it takes to create the mood in the audience. The artistic and sports performance lasts from 1.5 to 2 hours without a break. If the performance is prolonged, the tempo will decrease.

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